

CONTRIBUTION TO THE DESIGN OF COMPOSITE STIFFENERS USING FINITE ELEMENTS.

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Abstract : Modeling facilities have been developed to facilitate the description of beam finite elements made of composite materials. An experimental program has been set up to check the efficiency of beam elements for the modeling of plate stiffeners. Experimental results are compared with the values obtained by FE analysis, using the SAMCEF software.

Like for other materials, composite panels must usually be stiffened to limit the stresses and deformations due to transverse loads, or to prevent instability under in-plane loads. The design of such stiffened plates is usually done with the help of a general-purpose finite element computer code, although specialised programs do exist, which are dedicated to this kind of analysis. The tools which are available in general codes for the modeling of the plate and stiffener system are, usually, two-dimensional plate or shell elements for the plate, and beam elements for the stiffener. The beam and the plate or shell element are connected together by a limited number of nodes where the stiffness characteristics of the beam are condensed and incorporated into the stiffness matrix terms.

Plate, shell and beam elements were originally developed for the analysis of isotropic, homogeneous, mainly metallic structures. Most modern codes include now more or less extensive facilities to take into account the composite laminated structure of the bi-dimensional elements, but the beam elements have not yet followed the pace and are still organised mainly for the use of metallic structures. This is the case especially in the SAMCEF code, which we use at CRIF, and which has received some audience in industry, mainly in Belgium, France and Germany.

The various beam models used in finite element codes have all been developed for homogeneous and isotropic materials, and one may wonder whether they are still satisfactory when they are applied to a composite, which is a highly non homogeneous and non isotropic material.

We decided to set up an investigation with a double objective:

- to improve the tools for the description of composite beam-section;
- to check the efficiency of the beam model when used to represent a composite plate stiffener.

For the first part, new commands were developed at the pre-processor level to assist in the description of the geometry of the cross-section of a beam, in the description of the material distribution across the section, and in the correct evaluation of the geometrical and mechanical characteristics, required for the calculation. The information about the geometry and structure of the cross section is stored in the problem data-base. New commands were also developed for the post-processor, to transform the forces and moments obtained at the connecting nodes into stresses in the various plies.

For the second part, an experimental program coupled to numerical simulations was prepared. It was decided to begin with the behaviour under transverse load. A series of stiffened plates has been submitted to a three points bending test, and the results compared with the prediction of a finite

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There were in fact two simulations: one based on an 'accurate' model, representing the plate and the stiffener with 3-D composite volume elements, and constituting the best possible representation of the structure;

the other model was built using plate/shell elements with beam elements for the stiffener. The beam section was described using the improved tools referred to earlier.

Pre- and post-processor commands for composite beams

A simple but efficient approach has been followed to describe the geometry of the cross section of the beam: in an y-z space, perpendicular to the beam axis, the shape is first reduced to a set of lines situated at mid-thickness of each element. All intersections of two segments and all extremities define a "node". If some of the basic lines are curves, they must be approximated by a set of straight lines, separated by additional nodes. The entire network may then be uniquely defined by the list of nodes and the list of linear elements linking two nodes. Each element is oriented from the first to the second node, and the positive normal to each element is oriented at 90 degrees counterclockwise from this direction. The system allows the description of closed or open sections. (fig 1)

For the description of the composite material, the user successively defines materials, plies and laminates. A material corresponds to a 0 degree individual layer, and is defined by longitudinal, transverse and shear moduli, and a Poisson's factor. A ply is an oriented layer of a given material, with a given thickness, and is therefore defined by an angle relative to the x-axis of the beam, a thickness and a material. A laminate is an ordered sequence of plies. The laminates are assigned to the various elements. The description is completed by the coordinates of the connecting point with the plate/shell elements, and by a code telling whether the section is open or closed.

From this geometric and structural description, the command computes the various properties of the section:

- A : cross section area
- EA,GJ,EI_y, EI_z : extensional , torsional and flexural stiffnesses;
- y_c,z_c , y_s,z_s: elastic center and : shear center coordinates
- a: direction of the principal axes
- GA_y, GA_z: shear stiffness

The computed values take into account the eccentricity of the stiffener relative to the plate mid-plane. In the case of closed sections, the computational routines make a topological analysis of the section to detect the presence of multiple closed cells and correctly evaluate shear flows

A special problem was posed by some sections which are open sections when they are used as a beam, but which become part of a closed section when they are used as a plate stiffener. The hat sections belong to this family. These sections are signaled by a special code, and the description of the section itself must be complemented by the description of the plate element forming the closing wall(s) of the section. The characteristics are then evaluated in a mixed fashion: the extensional and flexural stiffnesses, and the elastic center coordinates are computed for the open section, while the shear and torsional stiffnesses and the shear center are determined for the closed section.

Experimental program

To check the efficiency of the beam model, a series of test was made in 3 points bending. Three shapes were chosen for the stiffener cross-section (fig 2):

- a I shape, which is an open , symmetrical section ;
- a C shape, which is open and unsymmetrical;
- a hat shape. which forms a closed section when applied to the plate.

The beams were made in two different material configurations: one using a combination of glass unidirectional and fabric reinforcements, the other one combining glass and carbon reinforcements. The matrix was polyester in both cases. The plates were all similar, made of two layers of glass mat

sandwiched between two glass fabric plies in a polyester matrix. The stiffeners were fastened to the plates using an epoxy adhesive.

The combination of shapes and material configurations resulted into six families of stiffened plates, and each was submitted to 3 variants of the 3-points bending test: the plate was supported between two clamping devices, with a free span of 950 mm. The load was applied at mid-span in three different ways (fig 3) :

- in test # 1, the load was applied directly to the stiffener;
- in test # 2 , it was applied directly to the plate, symmetrically, astride the stiffener;
- in test # 3, it was also applied directly to the plate, but with an lateral eccentricity introducing a torsional effect.

The specimen were equipped with some displacement transducers, to record the vertical displacement of a few selected points, and with strain gages recording the strains in several points of the mid-span cross-section.

Finite elements simulations

The various test specimen were analysed using the finite element code SAMCEF. Two models were built for each specimen: one, using composite volume elements, did include a detailed meshing of the stiffener as well as of the plate, and was taken as the reference finite element solution. In the second model, beam elements were used for the stiffener and described using the new tools developed for that purpose. Each model was used to simulate the three types of loading, and the results of the simulations were compared to the experimental results. In the SAMCEF code, the material characteristics for composite materials must be introduced as layer properties, and the values actually used for the simulations were half-theoretical, half-experimental data. A total of six different layers have been used to manufacture the various specimen. The basic characteristics of these layers were introduced in a laminate analysis program and slightly adjusted in such a way that when combined in the sequence corresponding to the various laminates used in plates and stiffeners, they yielded predicted elastic characteristics corresponding to the average value obtained from traction tests.

The same ply data have been used for all simulation, neglecting the fact that actual laminate characteristics presented some dispersion.

Results

The comparison between the values predicted by the reference FE model and the values measured during the tests have been made at two levels:

- comparison between the test results and the values obtained with the reference 3-D model;
- comparison between the values predicted by the two models.

The results predicted by the reference models are globally in good accordance with the measured values for what concerns the behaviour of the central strip situated along the stiffener. The displacements and deformations of the plate are correct for the #1 test, but are largely overestimated in #2 and #3 situations as the FE analysis was made in first order linear mode. Due to the mode of application of the loads in #2 and #3 tests, the displacements become rapidly very large and should be evaluated using a non-linear analysis. It was verified for one test that a second-order non-linear analysis effectively led to a correct assessment of the transverse deflections.

The C-section stiffeners have proven almost impossible to manage correctly, due to their tendency to twist under bending. Indeed, in the test #1, the point where the load is applied to the stiffener is constantly changing due to the twist of the section. This twist causes in fact a modification of the geometry of the cross section which results in a continuous modification of the bending stiffness of the beam. This evolution of the stiffness is not taken into account in the model, which becomes rapidly inaccurate. Similar situations occur in the #2 and #3 tests. This once more confirms that such shapes are not very efficient stiffeners.

2 - When comparing the results predicted by the accurate model and the beam/plate model, it appears that the beam model gives results very similar to those of the 3-D model for what concerns the bending effects in the strip along the stiffener. The situation is not as good for the displacements of the plate outside the central strip. Indeed, the beam element is concentrated along the line joining the connecting nodes, and the information relative to the lateral extent of the stiffener is lost. The main effect of a stiffener takes place in the plane normal to the plate and containing the centerline of the stiffener.

Actually, most stiffeners do occupy a certain area of the plate, and have also some stiffening action in the transverse direction. This effect depends on the geometry of the stiffener. It is negligible for blade stiffeners, small for an L- or C-section, medium for an I-section, and high for hat or box sections. When the stiffened plate is submitted to transverse loads, the transverse deflection of the plate is the sum of the deflection of the stiffened edges and the local deflection of the panels relative to these edges. This last component depends on the span between the stiffeners. Some stiffeners have a width which may be a fair percentage of the theoretical span (10 to 15 %), so that the actual unstiffened span of a panel may be 85 to 90 % of the theoretical span. This isostatic component may therefore be overestimated by a factor of 2 or even more, leading to an overdesign of the plate. (fig 4)

Conclusions

New tools have been developed for the description of beam-type finite elements with a composite structure. When used to model plate stiffeners, such elements behave satisfactorily in bending situations, but do not represent correctly the effect of the lateral extent of the stiffener, and therefore lead to an overestimation of plate displacements under transverse loads.

FIG. 1

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Type I

Type U

Type OMEGA

FIG. 2